

Ecole Supérieure de Journalisme de Paris

Deanship of Graduate Studies

Journalism Specialization

**Globalization Changing Social Values in Arab States and Societies in the 21st
Century**

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Introduction

The emergence of globalization in the middle of the last century – after the victory of the United States of America in the Second World War – brought new values to the world, known by famous political terms such as Americanism, Al-Makdala, and Al-Kawla (Al-Maysari, 2007).

These labels have come to be associated with people's social lifestyles, which is a reference to the McDonald's restaurant, which the sociologist George Ritzer has seen as a change in management and thinking style, and its symbolism that we have what has become known as fast food.

As for the cola, relative to the Coca-Cola drink, it means imposing the American social lifestyle in the world, while the Americanization means colonialism in itself.

Globalization and Internet technology, led by the United States of America after the Internet was a military weapon in the hands of the Soviet Union, managed to make it an intellectual weapon to spread globalization.

Today, we have many concepts that refer to the impact of globalization in the fields of life, including political, economic, technological and cultural globalization... etc.

Since we are talking about ethics and social values, we will talk about the impact of globalization in all its fields on the social values of individuals.

Technological Impact

Globalization has divided the societies of the world into two parts: the information society, which is the society that emerged after the Internet revolution, and the industrial and agricultural society that existed before the existence of the Internet.

The technological impact on the social lifestyle has become clear. We note that the independence, interdependence and social relations in our societies differ according to the different areas and identity that have been characterized by the entry of technology into each other. We have the urban and Bedouins, and we have the countryside and cities. The independence of personal life in the desert and rural community, where technological activity is almost absent. Because the family works as one beehive, and lives in one house, and the elderly man is the property of the family, he is keen to ensure that his kingdom is not separated. Independence is hostile to the social characteristics that the desert and rural people are familiar with, unlike cities, especially coastal areas and civilized capitals associated with technology. Because of technology, mixing and the different life systems in them, individuals find independence from their families once married.

Interdependence is a significant phenomenon in rural and desert society, as it is based on the agricultural and pastoral professions, unlike urban dwellers, who are less dependent due to weak social ties.

Hence, it can be said that the events of current life have changed the image of social relations between society. In cities, social media has become a bridge for establishing social relations, in addition to direct sessions on dining tables and outside the home, which are still present today in the countryside and the desert.

The relationship between independence and interdependence in the presence of technology is a direct one. The more self-sufficient a person is through independence, the less dependence he has on others, and vice versa. From my point of view, and in light of the current living conditions that afflict Yemen as a whole, the Bedouin and rural model has proven its cohesion in the face of these crises through interdependence. As an example, in the community of Wadi Hadhramaut (an agricultural community), the population is keen to give money to the family, one of whose members is getting married, and the gifting process takes a circular form among the members of that community that is trying to cohesion in the face of its economic crises, and it did not do so before this crisis (Ghanem, 2016).

As another example of the negative side of technological globalization, the rumors of the Corona pandemic and the Corona vaccines were a good example of this, as these rumors hinder the health efforts of the World Health Organization in limiting the spread of the pandemic, as well as encouraging people to take the vaccine.

At first, things allowed a person to open an account under a pseudonym without linking his account to his phone number, or with an email with a known identity, but with every blur that appears on the horizon, technology was keeping pace with fighting this phenomenon, and the best example of this was the researcher recounting in every training he conducts for novice journalists in fact-checking the incident of what was known as the kidnapping of two Yemeni girls in 2018, when one of them posted under a pseudonym on the Yodel application a picture of two girls on a Hilux car and wrote a comment that they were Yemeni girls, so that the media conflict between the Saudis and Yemenis began, and ended with the denial of Yodel's application for the incident, after the intervention of Saudi cybersecurity.

This is proof that misinformation is a way to spread hatred and enmity, and some news makes your opponent mock you and increase his popularity because of lies, and this is another example that testifies to this, which is the interruption of the Internet in Yemen for a month and a half in 2020, and the confusion raised about that.

Yemeni newspapers, as usual, obsessed with the field of fame, rushed to say that the Houthis, who control communications and the Internet in Yemen, did not pay \$150 million to the international companies that provide the Internet. Others went on to say that the companies demanded the Houthis to pay \$150 million for maintenance of the Falcon cables that provide Yemen with the Internet.

However, it turns out that all this claim is a lie, because the truth is that the interruption of the Yemeni Internet due to the anchor of a ship in the Red Sea, the interruption included many countries, but those countries have alternative solutions except for Yemen, and in response to a senior official at Oracle Company confirmed that the interruption is not strange, it happened that the Internet was cut off from Zimbabwe for hours because of a plowing machine in the neighboring country that was used by the tractor deeply, which led to the interruption of cables.

A Western expert at Oracle International charged Yemen's politicians with the deterioration of the Internet due to the weakness of the infrastructure that does not provide alternative lines for the continuation of the Internet, while Oman Telecom

(Sultanate of Oman) rushed to extend an emergency line to Yemen by 20% of the total volume of the Internet.

This is why the researcher criticizes media professionals who do not scrutinize what is published on the Internet, in an interview with Radio (Nama) in Hadramout, eastern Yemen, during the period of Internet outage.

From here, we know the phrase (the Internet is a double-edged sword), and therefore there are associations and organizations concerned with media literacy and digital literacy to form information health in the souls of the digital society.

Cultural impact

Globalization has shaped many cultural manifestations that promote the world from within the United States of America, some of which were considered against values and morals such as homosexuality, and others in favor of values and morals such as freedom and rejection of violence.

It was one of the manifestations of colonialism or occupation in the Arab world after the Picot Agreement that changed the social values of those Arab societies, and the introduction of secular values to some of those countries, as the French occupation did with Tunisia, for example, which is still controversial today, especially with the referendum on the new constitution under Tunisian President Qais Saeed, who considers Islam as the religion of the nation, not the state, which made his opponents believe that this is a change in the values of society.

Cultural globalization in short is the offer of crumbs in exchange for the occupier taking from you the most precious thing you have, and there is nothing in the cultural aspect of societies that they have more precious than their values, heritage and traditions, in exchange for promoting expatriate values that were not known before.

If we take something from these social values, which is accepting same-sex marriage and coexistence with them, it is a value that is being promoted now, especially with the approach of the World Cup in Qatar.

Lobby groups supporting homosexuality have sought to adopt draft laws to be voted on in European parliaments, and the United States of America is the official sponsor of homosexuality under former President Barack Obama.

However, as the wave of homosexuality crept into the Middle East and East Asia, this wave met strong opposition, as many countries criminalized homosexuality, and everyone noted that the State of Kuwait indicated in its State Department statement to the US Embassy in Kuwait that they should respect the social values of Kuwaiti society and not promote homosexuality, whether by raising the gay flag on the embassy, or through Twitter posts.

China – America's most prominent enemy – has also criminalized such behavior, banning homosexuals from appearing on its television screen.

But since the United States of America controls global decision-making, it wants to pass through the United Nations an international project that adopts homosexuals under many terms such as identity and sexual orientation.

As another example of the role of globalization in shaping social values and morals, what is known as modernists, who emerged since the advent of European colonies to the Arab world and during the two world wars, and their goal is to change the features of traditional societies to become a new European pattern, and writer Hassan Mneimneh (2018) states in an article on the American Al-Hurra channel that the emergence of modernists has had a cultural impact on Arab societies, as he pointed out that modernity is a system, a form and a culture, and that Arab countries have embraced it in form and systems and refrained from it as a culture.

For anthropologists, modernists are against anything conventional, even religion itself, and their lives are coupled with the pragmatic theory that the basis of coexistence is the existence of interests.

Modernists are a manifestation of the cultural globalization that preceded the technological globalization associated with the emergence of the Internet.

Economic Impact

In the classification of any country, we must look at six things that affect the national economy of peoples, the first of which is water and electricity, followed by health, education, roads and minerals. All countries share the interest in this classification in terms of activating human and material resources.

This classification can be called the six-way development, and in terms of studies and research, four senior officials of the International Monetary Fund called for it under the framework of the Sustainable Development Goals in a scientific article entitled: Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals will require an exceptional effort from everyone, and this article was directed especially to developing countries suffering from the economic effects of the Covid-19 pandemic, in which researchers called on developing countries to invest in social development and physical capital related to the six aforementioned areas, noting that it will be delayed for ten years without reaching the Sustainable Development Goals if there are no joint efforts between the international community to contain the repercussions of the economic pandemic, referring to the statement of the professor of economics at Columbia University and winner of the Noel Prize in Economics Joseph Stelts when he said: The only prosperity that is considered real and sustainable is the prosperity that everyone shares.

To give an example, in the previous years of its military presence in Afghanistan, the US Treasury announced that the mineral wealth in the ground is estimated at three trillion dollars, so where is the imbalance in the development and growth that Afghanistan is supposed to experience?

The theory of dependence (a political and economic theory) prevailed in Afghanistan in the Soviet, Taliban and American eras, all of which share the depletion of the surplus of this country in favor of its own agenda, in addition to the fact that the opium trade (drugs) was not a taboo there, so the destruction of the Afghan people apart from underground resources to be preoccupied with the conflict and the trade of deadly poison above the ground, this has become known as social values that define the identity of Afghans in front of the world, and let's not forget that the drug trade and use in any case will affect the system of morals and social values in the society in which this opium is rampant.

Media Influence

The media was not isolated from its use by globalization to influence the societies of the developing world. For example, in the book "The Art of Journalism" by the Egyptian researcher Farouk Abu Zeid, he pointed out that development journalism or journalism in the developing world is one of the schools of journalism that emerged in the twentieth century (before the advent of globalization). He said in his definition of this type of journalism (Abu Zeid, p. 53): A report that describes in accuracy, objectivity, an incident, an incident, or a valid idea that affects the interests of the largest number of readers, and it raises their interest, inasmuch as it contributes to the development and promotion of society.

Dr. Zaid (2011, p. 58) also pointed out that the commitment of news in developing societies to contribute to the development and promotion of society is not due to any kind of authoritarian or ideological (obligation), but is a professional commitment to the free national will of the journalist, which stems from his awareness of the needs of his developing society and his special circumstances, and (obligation) also means preference between events according to the extent of their contribution to the development of society.

In one of the articles published by the researcher on the "I want" scientific platform, he explained that the values of globalization have invaded the press (Al-Bayti, 2022). We find in the definition of journalism among the representatives of the Arab school affected by liberal thought that they know the news with a set of values that concern the reading community, including novelty, wit, strangeness, and excitement, and some of them have reached the point that they call for absolute and irresponsible freedom to respect the values of society.

As the researcher explained to an article by one of his professors in journalism, Dr. Anwar Mabrouki – a specialist in audiovisual media – describes the situation of cinema in Tunisian society, and the impact of cinema on social values, where he criticized Dr. Congratulations on promoting anomalous aspects such as sex at the expense of the values of society, including framing talk about women in their external form. The reason for this is foreign support for Arab cinema in light of the lack of local support for Arab cinema.

References

Al-Masiri, Abdul Wahab. (2007, May 29). *Americanization, kokala, and secularization*. Al Jazeera Network. Retrieved from link:

<https://www.aljazeera.net/opinions/2007/5/29/%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A3%D9%85%D8%B1%D9%83%D8%A9-%D9%88%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%83%D9%88%D9%83%D9%84%D8%A9-%D9%88%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B9%D9%84%D9%85%D9%86%D8%A9-2>

Ghanem, Abdul Karim. (2016). *Political awareness in Yemeni society*. Beirut, Lebanon: Arab Center for Research and Policy Studies.

Mneimneh, Hassan. (2018-May-23). *What is' modernity'? Where are we?* Al-Horra channel Retrieved from link:

<https://www.alhurra.com/different-angle/2018/05/23/%8A%D9%85%D8%A7-%D9%87%D9-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AD%D8%AF%D8%A7%D8%AB%9F%D8%A9%D8-%8A%D9%88%D8%A3%D9%D9%86-%D9%86%D8%AD%D9%86-%D9%85%D9%86%D9%87%D8%A7%D8%9F>

Sinhaji, Abdelhak and Benedik, Dora and Gemayel, Edouard and Alexandre Timan. (2021 Apr 29). *Achieving the SDGs will require an extraordinary effort from everyone*. IMF. Retrieved from link:

<https://www.imf.org/ar/News/Articles/2021/04/29/blog-achieving-the-sustainable-development-goals>

Abu Zaid, Farouk. (2011). **Press Release Art (Second Edition, pp. 53-58)*. Cairo: The World of Books.

Al-Baiti, Hassan. (2022 Apr 16). *The impact of cultural globalization on the Arab media industry: Tunisia as a model*. Arada Scientific Platform, retrieved from the link:

<https://portal.arid.my/ar-LY/Posts/Details/aeaf3246-136b-424c-a2ce-5d63584a44d8?t=%D8%AA%D8%A3%D8%AB%D9%8A%D8%B1-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B9%D9%88%D9%84%D9%85%D8%A9-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AB%D9%82%D8%A7%D9%81%D9%8A%D8%A9-%D9%81%D9%8A-%D8%B5%D9%86%D8%A7%D8%B9%D8%A9-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A5%D8%B9%D9%84%D8%A7%D9%85-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B9%D8%B1%D8%A8%D9%8A-->

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Jodel app.[@jodelapp] (2018 Oct 29). Yudlersna in Riyadh. We have already published the latest developments in the case of the # kidnapping_of_two_children. The story is fabricated. Our cooperation with the authorities in Riyadh has confirmed this. This photo has been uploaded using a third-party app. Please do not trade fake news. Greetings from the entire Jodel team!. Tweet Retrieved from link:

<https://twitter.com/jodelapp/status/1056896181475917824>

Newman, Lily High. (13 January 2020) An undersea cable outage plunges Yemen into a days-long internet outage. The American Wired newspaper. Retrieved from link:

https://www.wired.com/story/yemen-internet-blackout-undersea-cable/?utm_source=twitter&utm_brand=wired&mbid=social_twitter&utm_medium=social&utm_social-type=owned&utm_campaign=wired